

25 significant beyond a threshold. Additionally, the decrease in the gas adsorption decay
26 factor enhances cumulative production. These results provide beneficial insights into
27 the optimization of microwave heating to improve the efficiency of shale gas
28 exploitation.

29 Keywords: Shale gas; microwave irradiation; relative humidity; matrix-fracture system

30 1. Introduction

31 Amid increasing global energy demand and mounting environmental pollution,
32 the transition towards cleaner and more efficient sources of energy has emerged as an
33 inevitable trend in global energy development [1, 2]. Shale gas, a promising natural gas
34 resource primarily composed of methane (CH_4), has attracted considerable attention for
35 its potential to reduce dependence on conventional energy sources, decrease
36 environmental pollution, and facilitate the transformation of energy structure [3]. It
37 predominantly exists as free or adsorbed gas within shale gas reservoirs, which are
38 typically characterized by low porosity and permeability, thus restricting gas mobility
39 and posing considerable challenges to exploitation [4-6]. To enhance the extraction of
40 shale gas, hydraulic fracturing, a critical technique for the development of
41 unconventional energy resources, has been widely applied in this area [7]. This
42 technique induces the formation of fractures by injecting fluids into the reservoir at high
43 pressure, which improves the mobility of shale gas and thus enhances the extraction
44 efficiency [8, 9]. Although this technique has been highly effective in the extraction of
45 free gas, it has limited impact on gas that exists in the adsorbed state, which ranges
46 from 20% to 85% portion of shale gas, resulting in under-exploitation of the resource

47 [10, 11]. In addition, the retention of fracturing fluids within the rock may cause the
48 water-lock effect, which decreases reservoir permeability and adversely affects the
49 subsequent gas flow and extraction efficiency [12-14]. Therefore, the innovation and
50 optimization of gas mining technologies have become the focus of recent research.

51
52 Fig. 1 Schematic of microwave heating to promote shale gas production

53 To tackle the above-mentioned challenges, microwave thermal stimulation has
54 been developed as a novel heating approach and an auxiliary technique to hydraulic
55 fracturing, which has attracted considerable attention in the field of shale gas extraction
56 in recent years [15]. Integrating microwave thermal stimulation with traditional
57 hydraulic fracturing provides innovative methods and solutions to enhance shale gas
58 production (see Fig. 1). The heating method employs microwaves, known as
59 electromagnetic waves with frequencies between 300 MHz and 300 GHz, that are
60 characterized by their excellent penetration capabilities [16]. When exposed to
61 microwave irradiation, polar molecules within the shale gas reservoir can effectively
62 absorb the microwave energy and convert it into thermal energy to realize rapid heating
63 [17]. Compared to traditional heating methods, microwave heating presents numerous

64 advantages, such as high efficiency, energy saving, selective heating, and easy control.
65 These properties position microwave thermal stimulation as a promising technological
66 tool for shale gas extraction.

67 Previous studies have made notable progress in the application of microwave-
68 assisted shale gas extraction. For example, Hu et al. [18] experimentally found that
69 microwave heating can induce rock rupture and create a dense fracture network,
70 therefore significantly improving the intrinsic permeability of shale. Also, this
71 technology enhances the connectivity of initially closed pores within the formation,
72 which is critical for shale gas flow [19]. Xu et al. [20] conducted a comparative analysis
73 of shale before and after microwave treatment, revealing a 16.38% reduction in the
74 maximum methane adsorption, highlighting the influence of microwave heating on the
75 adsorption and desorption behavior of methane. Further, Zhu et al. [21], using
76 numerical simulation, demonstrated that microwave irradiation can effectively increase
77 pore volume and fracture width, which are crucial for strengthening shale gas
78 production. Fianu et al. [22] established a fully coupled electromagnetic-thermal-fluid
79 model, underscoring that shale gas extraction can be significantly facilitated through
80 microwave heating. In addition to the above studies focusing on the thermal effect of
81 microwave irradiation, its significant influence on moisture within shale gas reservoirs
82 has also been explored. It was revealed that microwave heating can effectively alter the
83 moisture state, thus alleviating the water-lock effect as well as changing the
84 characteristics of water-gas two-phase flow [23]. The evaporation of liquid water in the
85 reservoir changes water saturation, which affects the production behavior of shale gas

86 [24]. Hu et al. [25] presented that increased moisture affects the microwave absorption
87 capacity within the reservoir, which in turn influences the heating effect. Notably,
88 although previous studies have provided preliminary insights into the thermal effects
89 of microwave heating and changes in moisture state within the shale, the combined
90 influences of these factors on the extraction efficiency of methane remain inadequately
91 explored.

92 This study aims to investigate the water-gas transport mechanism in shale gas
93 reservoirs under microwave heating and systematically evaluate the efficiency of shale
94 gas production during microwave-enhanced thermal recovery. A multiphysics fully
95 coupled numerical model is developed based on the theory of bi-porous medium, which
96 takes account of the characteristics of two-phase flow in shale gas reservoir, and
97 incorporates the interactions among electromagnetic field, solid deformation, fluid
98 transport, and heat transfer. Using the coupled model, the effects of microwave
99 irradiation on the evolution of various physical parameters in the reservoir are
100 thoroughly analyzed. Also, the role of microwave power on changes in moisture and
101 gas content within the matrix is investigated. Additionally, the study examines the
102 influences of permeability and relative humidity on the water-gas exchange process
103 between matrix and fractures, as well as the impacts of various parameters on the
104 efficiency of shale gas extraction. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows:
105 Section 2 details the governing equations for multiple fields. Section 3 illustrates the
106 coupling relationship of the multiphysics model, and presents the finite element
107 computational model as well as its validation. Thereafter, Section 4 provides

108 comprehensive analyses and discussions of the simulation results, while Section 5
 109 addresses the limitations of this study. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the key findings
 110 of the research.

111 2. Theoretical model

112 The construction of the theoretical model for shale gas reservoirs is based on the
 113 following assumptions: (a) the shale is treated as a bi-porous elastic continuous medium
 114 with a spatially uniformly distributed fracture system; (b) the strain computation in the
 115 shale obeys small deformation theory; (c) local thermal balance is assumed within shale
 116 gas reservoirs; (d) the gas phase is modelled as a mixture of dry methane and vapor;
 117 and (e) the solid, liquid and gas phases are treated as overlapping but distinct continuous
 118 media.

119 2.1 Electromagnetic wave transmission

120 The propagation characteristics of electromagnetic waves in free space are
 121 determined by Maxwell's equations, which are represented by the following set of
 122 equations [26]:

$$123 \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_E \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

124 where \mathbf{E} is the electric intensity, \mathbf{B} is the magnetic flux density, \mathbf{H} is the magnetic
 125 intensity, \mathbf{J} is the current density, \mathbf{D} is the electric displacement or flux density, t is time,
 126 and ρ_E is the electric charge density.

127 The above equations are complemented by the following constitutive relations

128 [27]:

$$129 \quad \mathbf{D} = \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \mathbf{E}, \quad \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mu_r \mathbf{H}, \quad \mathbf{J} = \sigma_E \mathbf{E} \quad (2)$$

130 where ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity, ε_r is the relative permittivity that can be determined
131 by $\varepsilon_r = \varepsilon' + j\varepsilon''$ with ε' being the dielectric constant of the material, ε'' the loss factor
132 of the material, and j the imaginary number, μ_0 is the vacuum magnetic permeability, μ_r
133 is the relative magnetic permeability, and σ_E is the electrical conductivity.

134 The Helmholtz vector equation, which describes the time-domain electromagnetic
135 wave problem, is derived by substituting the constitutive relation of Eq.(2) into Eq.(1)
136 [28, 29]:

$$137 \quad \nabla \times \mu_r^{-1} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) - k_0^2 (\varepsilon_r - \frac{j\sigma_E}{\omega\varepsilon_0}) \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad (3)$$

138 where $k_0 = \omega/c_0$ is the free space wave number, c_0 is the speed of light in vacuum, $\omega =$
139 $2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, and f is the frequency of electromagnetic waves.

140 The dielectric properties of shale gas reservoirs depend on the moisture content
141 and deformation under microwave irradiation [30]:

$$142 \quad \varepsilon_r^{1/3} = \sum_{i=s,w,g} a_i \varepsilon_{ri}^{1/3} \quad (4)$$

143 where $a_s = 1 - \varphi_m$, $a_w = S_{wm} \varphi_m$, and $a_g = (1 - S_{wm}) \varphi_m$, with φ_m denoting the porosity of the
144 matrix, and S_{wm} the water saturation of the matrix.

145 The conversion of microwave energy to thermal energy can be expressed as [29]:

$$146 \quad Q_E = 2\pi f \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon'' |\mathbf{E}|^2 \quad (5)$$

147 2.2 Rock deformation

148 For shale gas reservoirs, the volumetric strain resulting from gas adsorption-
149 desorption is considered negligible. Based on the elasticity theory of bi-porous media

150 and accounting for variations in stress, temperature, pore pressure, and moisture content
 151 within reservoirs, the constitutive equation describing the stress-strain relationship of
 152 shale is [31, 32]:

$$153 \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2G} \sigma_{ij} - \left(\frac{1}{6G} - \frac{1}{9K} \right) \delta_{ij} \sigma_{kk} + \frac{\alpha_{Ts} T}{3} \delta_{ij} + \frac{\alpha_m p_m}{3K} \delta_{ij} + \frac{\alpha_f p_f}{3K} \delta_{ij} \quad (6)$$

154 where the shear modulus G can be obtained from the elastic modulus E_s and the
 155 Poisson's ratio ν as $G = E_s / 2(1+\nu)$, K is the bulk modulus of shale, T is the temperature
 156 of shale, i and j indicate the direction of Cauchy stress, δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta, the
 157 stress trace $\sigma_{kk} = \sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}$, α_{Ts} is the coefficient of thermal expansion of shale, the
 158 biot coefficient of shale matrix $\alpha_m = 1 - K / K_m$ with K_m denoting the bulk modulus of
 159 shale skeleton particles, the biot coefficient of shale fractures $\alpha_f = 1 - K / K_f$ with K_f the
 160 bulk modulus of shale fractures, p_m is the pore pressure of shale matrix, and p_f is the
 161 pore pressure of shale fractures.

162 Neglecting the inertial effect, the stress balance equation for shale is:

$$163 \quad \sigma_{ij,j} + f_i = 0 \quad (7)$$

164 where σ_{ij} is the components of total stress, and f_i denotes the stress components due to
 165 body force.

166 Given the elastic deformation of shale is small, the strain-displacement
 167 relationship can be defined as [31, 32]:

$$168 \quad \varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad (8)$$

169 where u is the component of the displacement vector.

170 In matrix and fracture systems, the pore pressure is determined by the fluid
 171 pressure of gas and water [33, 34]:

$$\begin{cases} p_m = (1 - S_{wm})p_{gm} + S_{wm}p_{wm} \\ p_f = (1 - S_{wf})p_{gf} + S_{wf}p_{wf} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where p_{gm} and p_{gf} are the gas pressures in the matrix and the fractures, p_{wm} and p_{wf} are the water pressures in the matrix and the fractures, and S_{wm} and S_{wf} are the water saturation of the matrix and fractures, respectively.

According to Eq.(8), the volumetric strain of shale can be obtained as [35]:

$$\varepsilon_v = -\frac{1}{K}(\bar{\sigma} - \alpha_m p_m - \alpha_f p_f) + \alpha_{Ts} T \quad (10)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ is the average compressive stress.

Through combining Eqs. (6)-(8), a modified Navier-type governing equation for shale deformation based on the dual porosity model is derived [36]:

$$Gu_{i,kk} + \left(\frac{G}{1-2\nu}\right)u_{k,ki} - \alpha_m p_{m,i} - \alpha_f p_{f,i} - K\alpha_{Ts}T_{,i} + f_i = 0 \quad (11)$$

2.3 Porosity and permeability models

2.3.1 Porosity and permeability models of shale matrix.

The stress-dependent porosity of the matrix is described using the Cui-Bustin model [37, 38]:

$$\varphi_m = \varphi_{m0} \exp\left\{-B_m \left[(\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\sigma}_0) - (p_m - p_{m0}) \right]\right\} \quad (12)$$

where B_m is the pore compressibility of the shale matrix which is defined as $B_m = \alpha_m / (\varphi_{m0} K_m)$, and the subscript nought denotes the initial conditions.

Substituting Eq.(10) into Eq.(12) yields:

$$\varphi_m = \varphi_{m0} \exp\left\{B_m \left[K(\varepsilon_v - \varepsilon_{v_0}) + \frac{K}{K_m}(p_m - p_{m0}) - \alpha_f(p_f - p_{f0}) - K\alpha_{Ts}(T - T_0) \right]\right\} \quad (13)$$

The relationship between permeability and porosity size in the matrix is described by the following cubic law [39]:

193
$$\frac{k_m}{k_{m0}} = \left(\frac{\varphi_m}{\varphi_{m0}} \right)^3 \quad (14)$$

194 where k_m is the intrinsic permeability of the shale matrix.

195 Combining Eq.(12) and Eq.(14):

196
$$k_m = k_{m0} \exp \left\{ 3B_m \left[K(\varepsilon_v - \varepsilon_{v_0}) + \frac{K}{K_m}(p_m - p_{m0}) - \alpha_f(p_f - p_{f0}) - K\alpha_{Ts}(T - T_0) \right] \right\} \quad (15)$$

197 2.3.2 Porosity and permeability models of shale fractures.

198 Similarly, the porosity of fractures can also be defined by the Cui-Bustin model:

199
$$\varphi_f = \varphi_{f0} \exp \left\{ -B_f \left[(\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\sigma}_0) - (p_f - p_{f0}) \right] \right\} \quad (16)$$

200 where φ_f is the porosity of shale fractures, p_f is the pore pressure in shale fractures, and

201 B_f is the pore compressibility of shale fractures which can be calculated through $B_f =$

202 $\alpha_f / (\varphi_{f0} K_f)$.

203 Substituting Eq.(10) into Eq.(16) results in:

204
$$\varphi_f = \varphi_{f0} \exp \left\{ B_f \left[K(\varepsilon_v - \varepsilon_{v_0}) + \frac{K}{K_f}(p_f - p_{f0}) - \alpha_m(p_m - p_{m0}) - K\alpha_{Ts}(T - T_0) \right] \right\} \quad (17)$$

205 And according to the cubic law, the permeability of the fractures is:

206
$$k_f = k_{f0} \exp \left\{ 3B_f \left[K(\varepsilon_v - \varepsilon_{v_0}) + \frac{K}{K_f}(p_f - p_{f0}) - \alpha_m(p_m - p_{m0}) - K\alpha_{Ts}(T - T_0) \right] \right\} \quad (18)$$

207 where k_f is the intrinsic permeability of shale fractures.

208 2.4 Methane transport

209 The mass conservation equation of methane is as follows [40-42]:

210
$$\frac{\partial m_i}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_{ai} \mathbf{v}_{gi}) = Q_{gi} \quad (19)$$

211 where m_i is the methane gas content, t is the time, ρ_{ai} is the density of methane gas, \mathbf{v}_{gi}

212 is the seepage velocity of the gas, Q_{gi} is the gas mass source term, and the subscript, i

213 = m or f , denotes the matrix system and the fracture system, respectively.

214 Methane in shale gas reservoirs primarily exists in two forms, free gas and
 215 adsorbed gas, and gas adsorption is assumed to occur exclusively within the matrix
 216 system. The methane gas contents in the matrix and fractures are defined below [5, 43-
 217 46]:

$$218 \quad m_m = (1 - S_{wm})\phi_m\rho_{am} + \rho_{ga}\rho_s V_L \frac{K(T)p_{gm}}{1 + K(T)p_{gm}} e^{(-\lambda\phi_m S_{wm})} \quad (20)$$

$$219 \quad m_f = (1 - S_{wf})\phi_f\rho_{af} \quad (21)$$

220 where ρ_{ga} is the density of methane gas at standard conditions, ρ_s is the density of shale,
 221 V_L is the Langmuir adsorption volume constant, λ is the gas adsorption decay
 222 coefficient, and $K(T)$ is the temperature-dependent adsorption equilibrium constant
 223 which is expressed as:

$$224 \quad K(T) = K_0 T^{-2} e^{-\frac{E_{ads}}{RT}} \quad (22)$$

225 where K_0 is the pre-exponential constant, E_{ads} is the characteristic adsorption energy,
 226 and R is the universal gas constant.

227 The density of methane gas can be computed using the actual gas equation of state:

$$228 \quad \rho_{ai} = \frac{M_g}{Z_i RT} p_{gi} \quad (23)$$

229 where M_g is the molar mass of methane gas. Z_i represents the deviation coefficient of
 230 the real gas within the medium and can be determined using an empirical equation [47]:

$$231 \quad Z_i = 0.702(p_{pri})^2 e^{(-2.5T_{pri})} - 5.524 p_{pri} e^{(-2.5T_{pri})} \quad (24)$$

$$+ 0.044(T_{pri})^2 - 0.164T_{pri} + 1.15$$

232 where $p_{pr} = p_g/p_{cr}$ in which p_{cr} denotes the critical pressure of methane, and $T_{pr} = T/T_{cr}$
 233 with T_{cr} being the critical temperature of methane.

234 In the shale matrix, the form of gas flow is typically classified using the Knudsen
 235 number, which is expressed as [48, 49]:

$$236 \quad K_n = \frac{\lambda_n}{r} \quad (25)$$

237 where r is the characteristic length of the flowing medium, and λ_n is the mean free path
 238 of the gas molecules defined as follows [48, 49]:

$$239 \quad \lambda_n = \frac{K_B T}{\sqrt{2} \pi \sigma^2 p_g} \quad (26)$$

240 where K_B is the Boltzmann constant, and σ is the collision radius of the molecule.

241 Considering the influence of gas flow mechanisms, the effective permeability in
 242 the shale matrix is [50]:

$$243 \quad k_{mapp} = k_m \cdot f(K_n) \quad (27)$$

244 $f(K_n)$ is the permeability enhancement function [50]:

$$245 \quad f(K_n) = (1 + \xi K_n) \left(1 + \frac{4K_n}{1 + K_n} \right) \quad (28)$$

246 where ξ is a rarefaction coefficient.

247 The source term representing the gas mass transferred from the matrix system to
 248 the fracture system can be obtained based on the intermedia mass transfer theory [51]:

$$249 \quad Q_{gm} = -Q_{gf} = -\frac{G_{m-f} \rho_{am} k_{mapp} k_{gm}^r}{\mu_a} (p_{gm} - p_{gf}) \quad (29)$$

250 where G_{m-f} is the shape factor related to the average matrix block size. For matrix blocks
 251 equally separated by fractures, $G_{m-f} = 8/a^2$.

252 In the presence of two-phase water-gas flow within the shale gas reservoir, the
 253 seepage of gas equations in both the matrix and fractures is as follows:

254
$$\mathbf{v}_{gm} = -\frac{k_{mapp}k_{gm}^r}{\mu_a} \nabla p_{gm} \quad (30)$$

255
$$\mathbf{v}_{gf} = -\frac{k_f k_{gf}^r}{\mu_a} \nabla p_{gf} \quad (31)$$

256 where μ_a is the dynamic viscosity of methane gas, and k_{gi}^r is the relative permeability
 257 of the gas phase, which is represented by [52, 53]:

258
$$k_{gi}^r = \begin{cases} 1-1.1S_{wi}, & S_{wi} < 1/1.1 \\ eps, & S_{wi} > 1/1.1 \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

259 The relative permeability of the liquid phase is calculated through

260
$$k_{wi}^r = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{S_{wi}-S_{rwi}}{1-S_{rwi}}\right)^3, & S_{wi} > S_{rwi} \\ eps, & S_{wi} \leq S_{rwi} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

261 where S_{rw} is the residual water saturation.

262 Substituting Eqs.(20)-(33) into Eq.(19), the equations describing methane seepage
 263 in matrix and fracture systems can be obtained:

264
$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\varphi_m(1-S_{wm})\beta_{gm} + \frac{Z_m p_a T}{T_a p_{gm}} \frac{\rho_s V_L K(T)}{(1+K(T)p_{gm})^2} e^{(-\lambda\varphi_m S_{wm})} \right] \frac{\partial p_{gm}}{\partial t} \\ & + \left[(1-S_{wm}) - \lambda S_{wm} \frac{Z_m p_a T}{T_a} \frac{\rho_s V_L K(T)}{1+K(T)p_{gm}} e^{(-\lambda\varphi_m S_{wm})} \right] \frac{\partial \varphi_m}{\partial t} \\ & + \left[\frac{Z_m p_a}{T_a} \frac{\rho_s V_L K(T)}{(1+K(T)p_{gm})^2} \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{E_{ads}}{RT}\right) e^{(-\lambda\varphi_m S_{wm})} - (1-S_{wm})\alpha_{Tgm} \right] \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ & - \left[\varphi_m + \lambda\varphi_m \frac{Z_m p_a T}{T_a} \frac{\rho_s V_L K(T)}{1+K(T)p_{gm}} e^{(-\lambda\varphi_m S_{wm})} \right] \frac{\partial S_{wm}}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k_{mapp}k_{gm}^r}{\mu_a} \nabla p_{gm} \right) \\ & = -\frac{G_{m-f}k_{mapp}k_{gm}^r}{\mu_a} (p_{gm} - p_{gf}) \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

265
$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi_f(1-S_{wf})\beta_{gf} \frac{\partial p_{gf}}{\partial t} + (1-S_{wf}) \frac{\partial \varphi_f}{\partial t} - \varphi_f(1-S_{wf})\alpha_{Tgf} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \\ & - \varphi_f \frac{\partial S_{wf}}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{k_f k_{gf}^r}{\mu_a} \nabla p_{gf} \right) = \frac{G_{m-f}k_{mapp}k_{gm}^r}{\mu_a} (p_{gm} - p_{gf}) \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

266 where β_{gi} is the compression coefficient for methane gas, α_{Tgi} is the coefficient of

267 thermal expansion of methane gas, p_a is the standard atmospheric pressure, and T_a is
 268 the standard temperature.

269 2.5 Moisture transport

270 The overall moisture content in shale gas reservoirs consists of both vapor and
 271 liquid water forms:

$$272 \quad w_i(\phi_i) = \phi_i[\rho_{wl}S_{wi} + \rho_{gi}\omega_{vi}(1-S_{wi})] \quad (36)$$

273 where $w(\phi)$ is the overall moisture content, which can be derived from Fig. 2. ρ_w is
 274 the density of liquid water, ρ_g is the density of gas, and ω_v is the mass fraction of the
 275 vapor is denoted as:

$$276 \quad \omega_{vi} = \frac{M_v \phi_i C_{sat}}{\rho_{gi}} \quad (37)$$

277 where M_v is the molar mass of vapor, ϕ is the relative humidity, and C_{sat} is the saturation
 278 concentration of vapor. According to the ideal gas hypothesis:

$$279 \quad C_{sat} = \frac{p_{sat}(T)}{RT} \quad (38)$$

280 where p_{sat} is the vapor saturation pressure:

$$281 \quad p_{sat}(T) = 610.7[\text{Pa}] \times 10^{7.5 \times \frac{T-273.15[\text{K}]}{T-35.85[\text{K}]}} \quad (39)$$

282
 283 Fig. 2 Moisture content of shale (modified from Tang et al. [54])

284 The binary diffusion of vapor and methane (g_w) in the gas phase is expressed as

285 follows:

$$286 \quad \mathbf{g}_{wi} = -\rho_{gi} D_{effi} \nabla \omega_{vi} \quad (40)$$

287 The effective diffusion coefficient (D_{effi}) in unsaturated media is often associated
288 with the Millington Quirk model, denoted as [55, 56]:

$$289 \quad D_{effi} = D_0 \frac{(1-S_{wi})\varphi_i}{\tau_i} \frac{p_a}{p_{gi}} \left(\frac{T}{T_b} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (41)$$

290 where $D_0 = 2.5 \times 10^{-5}$ [m²/s] is the diffusion coefficient of vapor in the gas phase under
291 standard temperature and pressure conditions, T_b is the normal temperature and τ
292 denotes the tortuosity factor, which can be formulated as:

$$293 \quad \tau_i = [(1-S_{wi})\varphi_i]^{-\frac{7}{3}} \varphi_i^2 \quad (42)$$

294 The flow field \mathbf{v}_{wi} can be determined using Darcy's law to describe the convection
295 of liquid water driven by the total pressure gradient:

$$296 \quad \mathbf{v}_{wm} = -\frac{k_{wm}^r k_m}{\mu_w} \nabla p_{wm} \quad (43)$$

$$297 \quad \mathbf{v}_{wf} = -\frac{k_{wf}^r k_f}{\mu_w} \nabla p_{wf} \quad (44)$$

298 where μ_w is the dynamic viscosity of liquid water.

299 The water pressure is calculated from the difference between the gas pressure and
300 the capillary pressure:

$$301 \quad \begin{cases} p_{wm} = p_{gm} - p_{cm} \\ p_{wf} = p_{gf} - p_{cf} \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

302 where p_{cm} and p_{cf} are the capillary pressures in the matrix and fractures, respectively,
303 and can be obtained as follows:

$$\begin{cases} p_{cm} = -\frac{RT\rho_{wm}}{M_v}\ln(\phi_m) \\ p_{cf} = -\frac{RT\rho_{wf}}{M_v}\ln(\phi_f) \end{cases} \quad (46)$$

305 The capillary diffusion of liquid water in a reservoir is described through Kelvin's
306 law as [57, 58]:

$$\mathbf{g}_{wci} = \rho_{wi} \frac{k_{wi}^r k_i}{\mu_w} \nabla p_{ci} \quad (47)$$

308 Note that the moisture content in porous media changes with time, where the vapor
309 and liquid water in shale satisfy the mass conservation equation. The moisture change
310 in the matrix and fractures can be described using the governing equations below:

$$\frac{\partial w_m(\phi_m)}{\partial t} + \rho_{gm} \mathbf{v}_{gm} \cdot \nabla \omega_{vm} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_{wm} + \mathbf{v}_{wm} \cdot \nabla \rho_{wm} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_{wcm} = -Q_w \quad (48)$$

$$\frac{\partial w_f(\phi_f)}{\partial t} + \rho_{gf} \mathbf{v}_{gf} \cdot \nabla \omega_{vf} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_{wf} + \mathbf{v}_{wf} \cdot \nabla \rho_{wf} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_{wcf} = Q_w \quad (49)$$

313 where the first term on the left-hand side of the equation represents the rate of variation
314 in shale's water content, the second term denotes the convection of vapor, the third term
315 indicates the binary diffusion of vapor and methane gas, the fourth term describes the
316 convection of liquid water, and the fifth term shows the capillary diffusion of liquid
317 water in shale rock. The moisture mass source term, Q_w , is defined based on the theory
318 of mass transfer between media [51]:

$$Q_w = G_{m-f} \rho_{gm} D_{effm} (\omega_{vm} - \omega_{vf}) - G_{m-f} \rho_{wm} \frac{k_{wm}^r k_m}{\mu_w} (p_{cm} - p_{cf}) \quad (50)$$

320 2.6 Heat transfer

321 For heat transfer in geological reservoirs of bi-porous media and neglecting
322 thermal filtration effects, the total heat flow rate, q_T , is given by [28, 59]:

323
$$\mathbf{q}_T = -\kappa_{eq} \nabla T \quad (51)$$

324 The thermal conductivity coefficient

325
$$\kappa_{eq} = \theta_s \kappa_s + \varphi_m [(1 - S_{wm}) \kappa_g + S_{wm} \kappa_w] + \varphi_f [(1 - S_{wf}) \kappa_g + S_{wf} \kappa_w] \quad (52)$$

326 where the subscripts, s , w and g , represent the solid, liquid and gas phases, respectively.

327 κ is the thermal conductivity coefficient, and $\theta_s = (1 - \varphi_m - \varphi_f)$ is the volume fraction of
328 the solid phase.

329 Accounting for the coupling among temperature change, thermal deformation, and
330 convective heat transfer between methane and moisture in shale gas reservoirs, and
331 referring to the heat transfer equation for moisture-containing porous media
332 implemented in the COMSOL software, the energy conservation equation for shale gas
333 reservoirs is formulated as follows [14]:

334
$$\begin{aligned} & (\rho C_{eq})_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + K \alpha_T T \frac{\partial \varepsilon_v}{\partial t} - \kappa_{eq} \nabla^2 T + \\ & (\rho_{gf} C_g \mathbf{u}_{gf} + \rho_{wf} C_w \mathbf{u}_{wf}) \cdot \nabla T = Q_1 + Q_{evap} + Q_E \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

335 where the initial term on the left side of the equation signifies the rate of heat flux
336 alteration in response to temperature changes, the second term indicates the change in
337 heat due to thermal strain in the shale skeleton, the third term is the heat transfer term
338 in shale gas reservoirs, and the fourth term is a thermal convection term for gas and
339 moisture in shale. Q_1 represents the heat source term which accounts for the enthalpy
340 diffusion flux arising from the diffusion of vapor in the gas as well as the capillary flux
341 related to the liquid water in porosity. Q_{evap} is the heat source of evaporation and Q_E
342 the microwave heat source. C denotes the specific heat capacity, and $(\rho C_{ep})_{eff}$ is the
343 effective specific heat capacity expressed as $(\rho C_{ep})_{eff} = \theta_s \rho_s C_s + [\varphi_m (1 - S_{wm}) \rho_{gm} + \varphi_f (1 -$
344 $S_{wf}) \rho_{gf}] C_g + (\varphi_m S_{wm} \rho_{wm} + \varphi_f S_{wf} \rho_{wf}) C_w$.

345 The heat source term Q_1 can be computed as follows:

$$346 \quad Q_1 = -[(C_v - C_g)(\mathbf{g}_{wm} + \mathbf{g}_{wf}) + C_w(\mathbf{g}_{wcm} + \mathbf{g}_{wcf})] \cdot \nabla T \quad (54)$$

347 where C_v is the specific heat capacity of vapor.

348 The heat source of evaporation in the heat transfer equation is:

$$349 \quad Q_{evap} = L_v G_{evap} \quad (55)$$

350 where L_v (J/mol) is the latent heat of evaporation, and G_{evap} is the evaporation source

351 which can be expressed as:

$$352 \quad G_{evap} = G_{evapm} + G_{evapf} \quad (56)$$

$$353 \quad G_{evapf} = \frac{\partial[\phi_i \rho_{gi} \omega_{vi} (1 - S_{wi})]}{\partial t} + \rho_{gi} \mathbf{v}_{gi} \cdot \nabla \omega_{vi} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{g}_{wi} \quad (57)$$

354 3. Numerical simulation and model validation

355 3.1 Cross-coupling relationship

356 The shale gas reservoir absorbs electromagnetic wave energy and converts it into
 357 heat, which raises the reservoir temperature and promotes methane desorption. This
 358 temperature increase induces the evaporation of liquid water, altering the relative
 359 permeability of the reservoir and consequently affecting the flow behavior of the water-
 360 gas two-phase system. Additionally, the elevated temperature causes thermal expansion
 361 of the reservoir, which leads to changes in the porosity and permeability that influence
 362 the transport properties. Meanwhile, variations in transport properties impact the
 363 dielectric characteristics and microwave absorption efficiency of the reservoir, which,
 364 in turn, will influence the efficiency of microwave heating. To capture the intricate
 365 interactions among electromagnetic field, solid deformation, moisture transport,
 366 methane transport, and heat transfer during microwave irradiation, Eqs. (3), (11), (34),

367 (35), (48), (49) and (53) are integrated to develop a fully coupled multiphysics model
 368 for the matrix-fractures system, as shown in Fig. 3. The coupled physical processes
 369 involve five sets of nonlinear partial differential equations with complex boundary and
 370 initial conditions, posing significant computational challenges. To address this,
 371 meshless methods have demonstrated capabilities in solving discontinuous and
 372 dynamic problems including gas-flow two-phase and wave transmission analyses [60-
 373 63]. The numerical simulations and analyses herein are performed using the finite
 374 element method implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics software given its strong
 375 abilities in solving multiphysics coupling problems.

376

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Fig. 3 Cross-coupling relationships among multiphysics fields

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3.2 Computational model

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380 Fig. 4 Computational model with boundary conditions of microwave-assisted shale gas extraction

381 To comprehensively investigate the water-gas exchange mechanism between the
 382 matrix and fractures in shale gas reservoirs under microwave irradiation, and to evaluate
 383 its influences on the efficiency of shale gas extraction, a coupled numerical model
 384 integrating multiphysics interactions is constructed. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the
 385 computational model is designed with dimensions of 50 m × 50 m to ensure the
 386 representativeness and applicability of the simulation results. For the simulation of the
 387 electromagnetic wave transmission field, scattering boundary conditions are applied to
 388 all boundaries except four waveguide ports, with two located on boundary AB and the
 389 other two on CD. This configuration enables a more accurate representation of the
 390 propagation characteristics of electromagnetic waves within reservoirs, as well as the
 391 mechanisms of energy transmission and absorption during the interaction between
 392 microwaves and the shale medium. The boundary conditions for other physical fields
 393 and the simulation parameters are detailed in Table 1 and

394 Table 2, respectively.

395 Table 1 Boundary conditions of the computational model (except for electromagnetic field boundary
 396 conditions described in the text)

Boundary	Rock deformation	Methane transport	Moisture transport	Heat transfer
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AB	Roller support	No flow	No flow	Insulation boundary
BC	Stress boundary	Flow boundary	Flow boundary	Insulation boundary
CD	Stress boundary	No flow	No flow	Insulation boundary
DA	Roller support	Flow boundary	Flow boundary	Insulation boundary

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Table 2 Numerical simulation parameters

Parameter	E_s	ν	K	K_m	K_f	α_{Ts}
Value	20	0.25	13.79	37.82	42.6	3.0×10^{-5}
Unit	[GPa]	-	[GPa]	[GPa]	[GPa]	[K ⁻¹]
Parameter	φ_{m0}	φ_{f0}	L_m	ϕ_{m0}	ϕ_{f0}	k_{m0}
Value	0.03	0.04	0.25	0.4	0.4	1.0×10^{-21}
Unit	-	-	[m]	-	-	[m ²]
Parameter	k_{f0}	p_{gm0}	p_{gf0}	T_0	ρ_s	V_L
Value	5.0×10^{-18}	30	30	353.15	2400	0.006
Unit	[m ²]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[K]	[kg/m ³]	[m ³ /kg]
Parameter	λ	D_0	K_0	K_B	S_{rwm}	S_{rwf}
Value	15	2.5×10^{-5}	0.1	1.38×10^{-23}	0	0
Unit	-	[m ² /s]	[MPa ⁻¹]	[J/ K]	-	-
Parameter	σ	C_s	κ_s	σ_{max}	σ_{min}	ε'_m
Value	0.38	1260	4	41.6	37.3	3
Unit	[nm]	[J/(kg·K)]	[W/(m·K)]	[MPa]	[MPa]	-
Parameter	ε'_g	ε'_w	ε''_m	ε''_g	ε''_w	
Value	1	$-0.2833T+80.67$	0.2	0	$0.05T+20$	
Unit	-	-	-	-	-	

399

3.3 Model validation

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To validate the accuracy of the multiphysics model, the simulation results obtained

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from the numerical model are systematically compared with the actual production data

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from the Barnett shale gas field [64, 65]. As shown in Fig. 5, the simulation curve of

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production rate aligns closely with the field production data throughout the entire

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production process, demonstrating the model's capability to accurately compute the

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dynamic characteristics of shale gas extraction. Further, Fig. 6 illustrates the impact of

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microwave heating on the gas production behavior of the well over the extraction

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process. The computational results indicate that during the short-term production phase

408 (0–2000 days), microwave heating has a limited effect on the gas production rate.
 409 Nevertheless, as the extraction progresses, microwave heating increasingly improves
 410 the methane production rate, which ultimately results in a 13.4% increase in cumulative
 411 methane production. This demonstrates the capability of the proposed multiphysics
 412 coupling model to capture the dynamic influence of heating on extraction efficiency.

413
 414

Fig. 5 Comparison of simulation results with Barnett Shale field production data

415
 416

Fig. 6 Effect of microwave heating on gas production behavior in gas wells

417 4. Results analyses and discussions
 418 4.1 Evolution of parameters at measurement points

419 The temporal evolution of various parameters, involving pore pressure, relative
 420 humidity, relative permeability, methane content, and vapor content, at two

421 measurement points are illustrated in Fig. 7. Fig. 7(a) shows the change of pore pressure
422 in the shale gas reservoir which presents a declining trend as the extraction process
423 progresses. Notably, pore pressure changes within the matrix exhibit an obvious lag
424 compared to those in the fracture regions. Furthermore, the lag effect becomes
425 increasingly pronounced as the measurement point is positioned closer to the hydraulic
426 fractures.

427 Fig. 7(b) presents that the relative humidity at the measurement points decreases
428 over time, which is mainly due to the gradual evaporation and outward transport of
429 water in the reservoir during the mining process. This reduction has a significant impact
430 on the fluid flow characteristics in both the matrix and fractures, as can be observed in
431 Fig. 7(c) and Fig. 7(d). Specifically, the decrease in relative humidity leads to a
432 considerable increase in the relative permeability of the gas phase, while the relative
433 permeability of the liquid phase progressively decreases.

434 The variation in methane content within the matrix for both free gas and adsorbed
435 gas is illustrated in Fig. 7(e). As pore pressure decreases, the adsorption capacity of the
436 matrix gradually weakens, resulting in a decline in adsorbed methane content within
437 the reservoir. In addition, the pressure difference between the matrix and fractures
438 drives the transport of free gas from the matrix to the fractures, which further
439 contributes to the reduction in methane content within the matrix.

440 Fig. 7(f) depicts the variation in vapor content within the reservoir. During the
441 initial stage of production, the vapor content remains relatively stable. However, over
442 time, the vapor content gradually decreases. Eventually, as the reservoir temperature

443 rises, the accelerated evaporation of liquid water reverses this trend, leading to a
 444 fluctuating increase in vapor content.

Fig. 7 Evolution of various parameters ((a) pore pressure, (b) relative permeability in matrix, (d) relative permeability in fractures, (e) methane content in matrix, and (f) vapor content at measurement points

451 4.2 Evolution of parameters along the measurement line

452 Fig. 8(a) presents the temperature evolution along the measurement line, which
 453 indicates that under microwave irradiation, reservoir temperature gradually increases

454 with prolonged heating. The non-uniform temperature distribution along the
455 measurement line is mainly attributed to the varying distance between different
456 reservoir regions and the microwave source, which results in a difference in
457 electromagnetic field intensity, and thus affects the heating efficiency in the medium.
458 Specifically, regions farther from the microwave source experience weaker dielectric
459 heating effects, leading to relatively smaller temperature increases.

460 As shown in Fig. 8(b), the methane adsorption content in the matrix decreases with
461 time. Along the measurement line, the adsorption content is the highest in the middle
462 and lowest at the sides, a pattern influenced by methane desorption from the matrix,
463 which is affected by the pore pressure. During the extraction process, regions farther
464 from the hydraulic fractures experience a slower rate of pore pressure reduction, leading
465 to a lower methane desorption rate, and therefore a smaller methane desorption rate.

466 Fig. 8(c) and Fig. 8(d) present the change in vapor content along the measurement
467 line in the matrix and fractures of the reservoir. The results reveal that areas remote
468 from the hydraulic fracturing zone have higher vapor content. During the initial 6000
469 days, the vapor content shows a decreasing trend, primarily due to the gradual loss of
470 vapor from the reservoir. However, after 8000 days, an increasing trend emerges, which
471 is attributed to elevated reservoir temperature facilitating the conversion of liquid water
472 into vapor. At this phase, the rate of vapor generation exceeds the loss rate, resulting in
473 a net increase in vapor content, which is consistent with the observations in Fig. 7(f).

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Fig. 8 Variation of parameters along the measurement line ((a) temperature, (b) methane content adsorbed in matrix, (c) vapor content in matrix, and (d) vapor content in fractures)

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4.3 Effect of microwave power

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As illustrated in Fig. 9(a), the methane exchange rate increases with rising microwave power. This phenomenon is attributed to the enhanced microwave energy at higher power levels, which elevates the substrate temperature. The temperature increase induces thermal expansion of the matrix, improving its porosity and permeability, and facilitating methane flow, thus enhancing the exchange rate. Moreover, the elevated temperature reduces water saturation in the matrix, bolstering the relative permeability of the gas phase, which further promotes gas exchange between the matrix and fractures.

Fig. 9(b) shows that the increase in microwave power reduces the amount of methane adsorbed in the matrix, revealing the relationship between microwave power

489 and methane adsorption/desorption. Specifically, as microwave power increases from
490 0 W to 120 W, the final methane adsorption in the matrix decreases from 43891 kg/m³
491 to 28618 kg/m³, corresponding to a 6.5% increase in desorption. This situation is mainly
492 caused by the matrix temperature escalation under intensified microwave power, which
493 accelerates the thermal motion of methane molecules to enable them to overcome the
494 binding forces at the adsorption sites more easily.

495 The variation in the moisture exchange rate under different microwave power
496 conditions is illustrated in Fig. 9(c). During the early stage of gas extraction (0–500
497 days), the short heating time results in a modest rise in reservoir temperature, and thus
498 the influence of microwave power on the moisture exchange rate is minimal. Beyond
499 500 days, the moisture exchange rate increases progressively with higher microwave
500 power. When $P_{in} \leq 30$ W, the low microwave power only induces a slow rise in reservoir
501 temperature, leading to a negligible enhancement in vapor diffusion, and consequently,
502 a limited improvement in the moisture exchange rate. As the extraction progresses, the
503 vapor concentration gradient between the matrix and fractures gradually diminishes,
504 which reduces the exchange rate. These combined factors result in an initial increase
505 followed by a decrease in the moisture exchange rate within this power range. For P_{in}
506 ≥ 60 W, the higher microwave energy rapidly raises the reservoir temperature,
507 improving the diffusion rate of vapor, hence facilitating the moisture exchange between
508 the matrix and fractures. This leads to a sustained increase in the moisture exchange
509 rate over time.

510 Microwave power also significantly influences the vapor content within the matrix

511 (see Fig. 9(d)). For $P_{in} \leq 30$ W, the temperature of the reservoir increases slowly, leading
 512 to a low evaporation rate of liquid water, with negligible evaporation occurring. Under
 513 these conditions, the vapor content within the matrix does not see an apparent increase
 514 during the extraction process. In contrast, when $P_{in} \geq 60$ W, the rapid increase in
 515 reservoir temperature accelerates the evaporation rate of liquid water. As the
 516 temperature continues to increase, the evaporation rate in the matrix eventually exceeds
 517 the rate of moisture exchange, making the steam content in the matrix rise.

518 Microwave power affects the methane and vapor content in the matrix by
 519 influencing reservoir temperature, and plays a crucial role in regulating both the
 520 methane and vapor exchange rates. The finding provides valuable insights for
 521 optimizing the application of microwave heating in the natural gas extraction process.

Fig. 9 Variation of methane and moisture contents in shale gas reservoir under various microwave

525

526 4.4 Effect of relative humidity

527 The influence of relative humidity on water-gas two-phase flow is studied. As
528 illustrated in Fig. 10(a) (for matrix) and Fig. 10(b) (for fracture), an increase in initial
529 relative humidity (RH_0) significantly affects the relative permeability of both gas and
530 liquid phases. Higher relative humidity increases moisture content and intensifies the
531 water-lock effect in the reservoir. Microwave irradiation elevates the reservoir
532 temperature, which promotes the evaporation of liquid water, and reduces water
533 saturation. This process mitigates the adverse impact of moisture on the relative
534 permeability of the gas phase, therefore enhancing gas mobility. Consequently, the
535 relative permeability of the gas phase gradually increases, while that of the liquid phase
536 decreases over time.

537 Fig. 10(c) indicates that an increase in initial relative humidity pronouncedly
538 reduces the methane exchange rate. Throughout the mining process, the methane
539 exchange rate experiences a trend of initially increasing and then decreasing. The early-
540 stage increase is driven by the rapid decrease in pore pressure in the fractures during
541 the initial production period, which amplifies the pore pressure difference between the
542 matrix and the fractures, hence enhancing methane exchange. Over time, however, the
543 pore pressure within the fractures stabilizes, reducing the pore pressure difference,
544 which subsequently results in a decrease in the methane exchange rate.

545 As shown in Fig. 10(d), for $RH_0 \geq 0.4$, the moisture exchange rate exhibits a pattern
546 of initially increasing, followed by a decline, and then a subsequent rise. Note that there
547 is a significant difference in moisture content between the reservoir and the external

548 environment at a high relative humidity level. During the early stage of production,
549 moisture exchange primarily occurs between the matrix and the liquid water in the
550 fractures. The significant pressure difference between the fractures and the external
551 environment drives liquid water in the fractures to rapidly flow into the hydraulic
552 fractures, which increases the pressure difference between the matrix and fractures,
553 causing a rapid rise in the rate of moisture exchange. As the liquid water in the matrix
554 gradually flows into the fractures, the pressure difference decreases, resulting in a
555 subsequent reduction in the moisture exchange rate. Thereafter, as extraction progresses,
556 moisture exchange shifts to occur mainly between the matrix and the vapor in the
557 fractures. The rising reservoir temperature and the decreasing pressure accelerate the
558 diffusion of vapor in the matrix, therefore considerably enhancing moisture exchange
559 and leading to a second upward trend of the moisture exchange rate. In contrast, when
560 $RH_0 \leq 0.3$, the difference in moisture content between the reservoir and the external
561 environment is relatively small. This results in a slower increase in the moisture
562 exchange rate, which is insufficient to produce the above-mentioned fluctuation
563 observed at high relative humidity. Consequently, the moisture exchange rate presents
564 a steady upward trend.

565 Fig. 10(e) illustrates the gas production rate decreases with increasing relative
566 humidity. This decline is attributed to high moisture content in the reservoir under high
567 relative humidity, which obstructs gas flow pathways and reduces methane production
568 efficiency. Additionally, Fig. 10(f) highlights the influence of relative humidity on the
569 contribution of different methane storage forms to cumulative methane production. The

570 contribution of free gas in the fractures is relatively small, while the majority of
 571 methane production originates from adsorbed methane in the matrix. As relative
 572 humidity increases, the proportion of adsorbed methane in total methane production
 573 also rises. Specifically, when relative humidity increases from 0.2 to 0.6, the proportion
 574 of adsorbed methane increases from 51.7% to 71.0%. This phenomenon is primarily
 575 due to that the high moisture content takes the space previously available for free gas,
 576 which leads to a notable reduction in free gas content within the reservoir.

577 Relative humidity significantly influences methane production. Effective
 578 management of relative humidity during the extraction process is essential for the
 579 optimization of methane recovery efficiency.

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Fig. 10 Effect of relative humidity on relative permeability, moisture and methane exchange rates, and methane production efficiency

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585 4.5 Effect of permeability

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Fig. 11 illustrates the influence of initial permeability in the matrix and fractures

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on methane recovery. As shown in Fig. 11(a) (matrix) and Fig. 11(c) (fracture), the gas

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production rate initially increases and then decreases. At the early stage of extraction,

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free gas in the fractures flows rapidly outward due to the pressure difference, resulting

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in a rise in the gas production rate. Nevertheless, as extraction progresses, pore pressure

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in the fractures gradually decreases, which leads to a corresponding reduction in the gas

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production rate. At this stage, there exists a pressure difference between the matrix and

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fractures, driving gas transport from the matrix to the fractures, where the gas is

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subsequently extracted. Increased matrix permeability strengthens the methane

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exchange rate, but reduces the peak production rate. This occurs because the accelerated

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gas exchange diminishes the pressure difference within the fractures, which lowers the

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extraction rate. In addition, increased fracture permeability improves gas flow in the

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fractures, thus positively contributing to the gas production rate.

599

Understanding the influence of reservoir permeability on cumulative methane

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production is essential. During the early stage of gas extraction, the increase in matrix

601 permeability has a relatively minor effect on cumulative methane production (see Fig.
 602 11(b)), while improved fracture permeability considerably boosts cumulative
 603 production (see Fig. 11(d)). Nonetheless, as extraction progresses, further increases in
 604 matrix and fracture permeability show a diminishing impact on the overall enhancement
 605 of methane production.

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608

Fig. 11 Effect of matrix and fracture permeability variation on methane production efficiency

609 4.6 Effect of gas adsorption decay coefficient

610 The gas adsorption decay coefficient is a pivotal factor for evaluating the influence
 611 of relative humidity on the adsorptive capacity of methane within the shale matrix. Fig.
 612 12 indicates that a decrease in this coefficient corresponds to an upward trend in
 613 cumulative methane production. Specifically, when the coefficient decreases from 25
 614 to 15, 30-year cumulative methane production increases by 6.0%, and a further decrease

615 from 15 to 5 results in an additional 6.5% increase. This trend occurs because a smaller
 616 gas adsorption decay coefficient weakens the dampening effect of relative humidity on
 617 the gas adsorption capacity of the matrix, which improves the adsorption efficiency.
 618 Consequently, more methane is initially adsorbed in the shale matrix, which leads to
 619 greater desorption during the extraction process and improves cumulative methane
 620 production. The results underscore the important role of the gas adsorption decay
 621 coefficient in affecting methane adsorption capacity and cumulative production.

622

623 Fig. 12 Effect of gas adsorption decay coefficient on cumulative methane production

624 5. Limitations

625 The proposed model integrates the complicated coupling process among multiple
 626 physical fields, however, certain limitations and shortcomings remain. Albeit the
 627 simulation accounts for the effect of relative moisture on gas adsorption/desorption in
 628 shale gas reservoirs, it does not consider the role of the moisture film structure in the
 629 matrix, which can influence gas release capacity and transport characteristics through
 630 modulating gas-solid interface interaction [66, 67], hence important for the analysis of
 631 methane extraction. Also, the impact of the initiation pressure gradient for gas seepage

632 on methane flow behavior within the fracture system is not included, which is directly
633 affected by the variation in reservoir moisture content [68, 69]. In addition, although
634 the theory of dual-porosity medium is employed herein as the fundamental framework
635 for fluid flow simulation in gas reservoirs, hydraulic fracturing in actual reservoirs can
636 generate a complex multi-scale discrete fracture network [70, 71], which significantly
637 influences the permeability of medium and transport characteristics of the fluid. To
638 tackle the aforementioned limitations and improve the accuracy and applicability of the
639 approach, future research will focus on developing a refined model to better capture
640 these multi-scale nonlinear factors. Such advancements will enable a more precise
641 description of the complex flow behavior and reservoir response.

642 6. Conclusion

643 Based on the dual-porosity theory and incorporating electromagnetic effects, solid
644 deformation, heat transfer, methane transport, and moisture transport, this study
645 develops a comprehensive multiphysics coupling model for the analysis of shale gas
646 exploitation. Using finite element numerical simulation, the evolution of various
647 parameters in shale gas reservoirs is systematically investigated, with particular
648 emphasis on the micro-mechanisms of water-gas interaction within the matrix and
649 fractures. In addition, this study systematically examines the influences of relative
650 humidity, microwave power, permeability of matrix and fractures, as well as gas
651 adsorption decay coefficient on methane production. The main conclusions drawn from
652 the computational results are as follows:

653 1) Relative humidity considerably impacts shale gas production efficiency in two

654 primary aspects. First, it substantially alters the relative permeability of shale
655 gas reservoirs, influencing the water-gas exchange rate between the matrix and
656 fractures, and consequently, the efficiency of methane production. Second,
657 relative humidity also has a pronounced effect on the storage form of methane
658 in shale gas reservoirs, particularly the proportion of adsorbed methane in total
659 methane production. As relative humidity increases from 0.2 to 0.6, the
660 proportion of adsorbed methane in total production notably rises from 51.7%
661 to 71.0%.

662 2) Microwave heating markedly influences the diffusion rate of vapor and the
663 evaporation rate of liquid water, and thus affects the moisture content in the
664 shale gas reservoir, particularly during the later stage of production. At low
665 input power, the moisture exchange rate initially increases and then decreases,
666 while the vapor content in the matrix steadily decreases. For high input power,
667 the moisture exchange rate continuously rises, while the vapor content in the
668 matrix first decreases before increasing. Furthermore, microwave heating can
669 enhance the methane exchange rate between the matrix and fractures,
670 meanwhile improving methane desorption capacity. As the microwave power
671 increases from 0 W to 120 W, methane desorption increases by 6.5%, which
672 effectively boosts the efficiency of methane production.

673 3) The rate of methane production is closely related to reservoir permeability,
674 which displays a trend of initially increasing and subsequently decreasing as
675 permeability rises. During the early stage of extraction, enhanced fracture

676 permeability boosts both the methane production rate and cumulative methane
677 production. Also, increasing matrix permeability can accelerate the methane
678 exchange rate between the matrix and fractures, thus improving the production
679 rate at the middle stage. Nevertheless, change in reservoir permeability has a
680 limited effect on the enhancement of cumulative production. Therefore, the
681 optimization of methane production necessitates careful management of
682 reservoir permeability.

683 4) A reduction in the gas desorption coefficient improves matrix adsorption
684 capacity, therefore positively influencing cumulative methane production.
685 Specifically, when the coefficient decreases from 25 to 5, 30-year cumulative
686 methane production increases by 12.5%.

687

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